

ISic3689

I.Sicily inscription 3689

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Quarry of the Intagliatella

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 92 + 6474

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140538

1. ἐνθ[ά]δε κῆτε Μαρκιανή
2. □ σεμνή [κ](αὶ) ἄμεμπτος βιώσ [ασα]
3. ἰς τὸν κόσμον τοῦτον· ἄπε #⁷ -
4. χώρι ²⁶ἀπεχώρι²⁶ πρὸς [τ](ὸν) [Κ]ύριον ἐτῶν
5. α □ ω ι#⁵⁶α', [ψυ]χὴν π[ρολιπ]οῦσα τῆ
6. πρὸ θ καλ (ανδῶν) Ἰανουαρ-
7. ἰων. τὸν δὲ θεόν σε, φίλε,
8. μή μου σκύλης τὸν βόθ-
9. ρον, μή μοι δίξης φῶς·
10. ἄ[ν]] δὲ θελήσης φοῦς ²⁶φῶς²⁶ μοι
11. δίξε, σοὶ τὸ φῶς
12. ὁ θ (εὐ) ς ΧΟΛΙ[.]ΟΝ ²⁷χόλιον?²⁷ δώση.
13. □ ἰχθύς ²⁶Ι(ησοῦς) Χ(ριστὸς) θ(εοῦ) υ(ἰὸς) σ(ωτήρ)²⁶.
14. ²palmula²
- 15.

Edition: PHI175477

1. ἐνθάδε κίτε Μαρκιλίνη,
2. □ σεμνή κ(αί) ἄμεμπτος βιώσα (σα)
3. ἰς τὸν κόσμον τοῦτον. ἀπε[κ]-
4. χώρι πρὸς [Κ]ύριον ἐτῶν
5. ιζ' ΑΙΧΗΝ πράττουσα τῆ
6. ἀπὼ πρὸ θ καλ (ανδῶν) Ἰανουαρί-
7. ων. τὸν δὲ θεόν σε, φίλε,
8. μή μου σκύλης τὸν [β]όθ-
9. ρον, μή μοι δίξης φῶς.
10. ἂν δὲ θελήσης φῶς μοι
11. δίξε, σοὶ τὸ φῶς
12. ὁ θ (εὐ) ς χόλιον δώση.
13. ἀπὼ ΙΧΘΥC ²⁶Ι(ησοῦς) Χ(ριστὸς) θ(εοῦ) υ(ιὸς) σ(ωτήρ)²⁶.
- 14.

Apparatus**Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

PHI 140538

PHI 175477

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0238 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 14.0590

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1955.0307

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 4.9473

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.65

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.44 ph

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia. Vatican. At no.492

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3689. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388962>